

Simulating the resin transfer molding process with graph neural networks

Jimmy G. Jean, Guillaume Broggi and Baris Caglar
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Outline

1

Background

- Mold filling
- Machine learning and mold filling
- Graph neural networks

2

Microscale

Flow microstructures

- Surrogate model
- Results

3

Macroscale

Mold filling

- Surrogate model
- Results

Summary

Background: Resin transfer molding

Multiscale process

Resin transfer molding (RTM)

- is a **multiscale process**
- but **numerical simulations** that incorporate information from all scales are **time-consuming**

Can we make simulations faster with neural network, while keeping accuracy?

Background: RTM and machine learning (ML)

Micro-scale

An image-based deep learning framework for flow field prediction in arbitrary-sized fibrous microstructures ([under review](#))

Macro-scale

Stieber et al. (2021)

Research using ML to accelerate modeling typically focuses on **rectangular geometries**.

What about focusing instead on **arbitrary geometries**?

Background: Meshes are graphs

Manufactured composite parts mostly have **irregular shapes**

Numerical simulations based on the finite volume method (FVM) use **unstructured meshes**.

Mesh

Graph

What type of **neural network** operates on **graphs**?

Background: Graph neural networks

Graph neural networks operate on graphs

Message passing process

The message passing process naturally represents the flow of resin through a domain

Graph neural networks are thus perfect for simulating the mold filling process

Microscale: Dataset and Training

Microstructures

Parameter	Value
Fiber volume fraction	0,4
Fiber diameter	7 μm
Samples	1000

Simulation OpenFOAM

- Velocity-driven flow
- (left) Inlet velocity: $(10^{-4}, 0) \text{ m/s}$
- (right) Outlet pressure: 0 Pa
- Resin density: 1250 kg/m^3
- Resin viscosity: 0.5 Pa/s

Cost function

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y - \tilde{y})^2}$$

Encoder-Processor-Decoder

Training / validation split: 80% / 20%

Microscale: Results

Histogram of errors
(normalized)

Examples

from training set

from validation set

Macroscale: Dataset

Convex shapes

Polygon smoothing: centripetal Catmull-Rom splines*

For each shape

- Circle radius: 0,5 m
- # of points sampled: 7

Dataset

- Training: 1000 shapes
- Test: 100 shapes

Simulation settings

- Resin viscosity: 0.1 Pa.s
- Fiber volume fraction: 0.6
- Permeability: $6.8e-10 m^2$
- Layup angle of fabric: 0
- Mold thickness: 5 mm
- Injection pressure: 1 bar

Injection point placed at far-left

Simulation tool: RTM-Worx by

Macroscale: Neural Network architecture

Model training

Macroscale: Model performance

The trained model

1. is able to give **realistic flow evolution** (although imperfect)
2. noticeably underestimates the filling time

Macroscale: Extrapolation

Concave shape

- Characteristic length **2X** what encountered in dataset
- Filling time **3X** what encountered in dataset

Summary

We introduced

1. A **graph neural network** for (steady-state) flow prediction at the **microscale**
2. A **graph neural network** to model mold-filling at the **macroscale**

The preliminary results show the potential of the approach for simulating the **resin transfer molding process** at multiple scales.

Thanks, looking forward to your questions!

Outlook: Multiscale surrogate

Special thanks to

Contact

LinkedIn

Email: j.g.jean@tudelft.nl